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BA program

**A macroeconomic study into:
-Romania's post-communist transition-**

Regarding

**Evolutions and implications generated, in
crisis contexts, at the level of the national
economy and viable solutions for a quick
return on an upward trend**

From a communist led economy to a national economic revival; a true display of evolution. This transformation was not merely a shift in ideology, but a complex reconfiguration of Romania's economic order. The change-off that occurred into the market mechanisms, institutions and practices, those that used to be the roots of our economic instability (for e.g. output decline, national and foreign debt, unemployment, high inflation) laid the foundations for long term economic growth, along with gradual integration into the global market and evidently, EU affiliation. Romania's the perfect example of how open and smaller sized economies are more vulnerable to global shocks compared to larger economies, and how effective external assistance and structural reforms can be. In this paper I will analyze the struggle of transitioning from a command economy to a free market economy, through macroeconomic lenses, by examining key indicators and policies that shaped Romania's post-communist evolution. First, it's important to understand how we ended up here.

After the end of WW2, poverty in Romania was closely tied to the country's political and economic system. The communist party, who was just appointed because it was trusted to reignite back the country at one of its lowest points in history following the misfortunes of the interwar period, the great depression crisis, the heavy military burden (i.e. a large share of the national budget went into military spending rather than civilian needs), the oil and grain exploitation at the hands of the nazi army, food shortages, soviet occupation (which resulted in both bloodbaths and huge reparations fees in addition to exploitative use of our national resources) and overall distraught economy and morale, ended up confiscating all means of production and implementing new land reforms. Until 1972 they prioritized paying off war debts and converting the last pieces of national wealth we had left into state property. Food staples rose up to 1000%, Romanians average annual per capita consumption decreased by 20% and food supply shortages now became a normality. While the government was sending 50% of our exports to the USSR to pay off debts; this was the reality of the Romanian population. The country that used to be known as the "breadbasket of Europe" was now without grain. This is the living standards which 55.8% of Romanians consider superior to our current status, according to INSCOP. Child mortality was 2/3 higher than it is today, and the average life expectancy was 10 years less, and yet, 48.6% of the polled subjects consider that health access was better back then. But let's not forget the cherry on top; 45% of my peers, the younger generation, men and women from the ages of 18 to 25, who grew up hearing their parents and grandparents' horror stories from these times, believe that communism was a good thing. The funny thing is, or should I say, depressing, is that the subjects of that survey who contributed

to that astonishing percentage, are either the uneducated masses, or the ignorant ones. I honestly don't know which one is worse; the ones who don't seem to have any interest in their countries past and prefer running with the first crumble of information they find online by mere chance, or the ones who disregard completely the populations quality of life for production results. It only looks good on paper, not in real life. I promise you if you had to wait in lines for up to 12 hours daily in order to get basic food items to get you through the week, thus missing your daily Starbucks run, shopping spree, or hours long calls on Discord while playing insipid videogames with your buddies, you would rapidly change your mind. Not to mention that your favourite capitalistic vice, your beloved gambling establishments like Superbet, would cease to exist since they are privately owned; I hope that puts things more into perspective for you. In any way, these groups of people, the ones who are clearly lacking any form of critical thinking process, regardless of their political affiliations and preferred pastimes, are exactly the reason why Romania is developing slower than other countries in eastern Europe. Nonetheless, let's see where we started.

In the winter of 1989, on the 22nd of December, Romania inherited a centrally planned economy with heavy debt, low productivity and chronic shortages. Not exactly a dream situation. Add to that the fact that they had lived like this for the past 42 years and that as far as market knowledge goes, most of them didn't know anything besides the way communism operates, and you got yourself severe social hardship, caused by economic contraction, hyperinflation, unemployment, fiscal and debt problems, and overall, catastrophic output. Everything that could've possibly gone wrong did, and because of this abrupt transition, the period that followed the transition definitely needs to be categorized as an economic crisis. By the end of the 90's, Romania was one of the poorest countries in Europe. The government struggled with deficits and foreign debt repayments, the state budget crises limited investment in infrastructure and social programs, GDP fell sharply and therefore Romania experienced a deep recession. Many state-owned industries collapsed under competition, inflation soared to over 200%, unemployment rose to double digits, poverty increased, and of course as a result, many people lost their savings due to inflation. The rise in unemployment was a direct cause of state-owned industries shutting down. During communism, the unemployment rate was near 0, and it reached its peak for that period in 1994, equalling 11%. Industrial production declined and agricultural inefficiencies compounded rural underemployment, creating both cyclical and structural unemployment.

Simultaneously, the liberalization of prices and the abandonment of state subsidies led to hyperinflationary pressures. The highest inflation rate was marked in 1993 at 256.1% shortly followed by the previous year at 210.4%. This inflationary surge eroded household purchasing power, disrupted savings, and called for urgent monetary stabilization measures, including tighter money supply controls and interest rate adjustments. The Romanian currency depreciation reflected both domestic imbalances and its exposure to foreign capital volatility, demonstrating the economy's sensitivity. The banking sector, previously an instrument of state planning, underwent some restructuring as well. Weak institutions and non-performing loans initially constrained credit creation, reducing private investment and limiting the economy's capacity to self-correct. In parallel, fiscal imbalances emerged as the state struggled to finance subsidies, social transfers and privatization processes, resulting in high deficits and growing public debt. The crisis context illustrated the interdependence of fiscal, monetary, and structural policies, where inadequacies in one sector could represent, and did in fact mean, systemic risk across the whole national economy.

GDP growth stayed negative from 1990 through 1992, the lowest percentage being recorded in 1991 at -12.9%. It gradually rose until 1996 when it started declining again, reaching negative rates from 1997 to 1999 (-6.1%, -4.8%, -1.2%). Even though in the year 2000 the unemployment rate was still high (7.6%) inflation started going down (45.7%) and GDP growth was eventually positive again (2.95%). This is when the economy finally started regaining its strength. The increase in GDP is a direct result of privatization and foreign investment.

However, the shift from the state's central decision making to that of private individuals/businesses along with price liberalization, the process of privatizing state-owned enterprises and opening the economy to foreign trade and investment, were all processes that didn't happen overnight. Romania adopted a delayed inconsistent gradualism, sometimes known as a "stop and go reform" which hurt them, since it's inefficient when compared to the standard transitional methods; shock therapy and gradualism. Shock therapy, as the name indicated, is fast-acting and brings instant price liberalization, quick privatization and fast currency convertibility, but causes deep crises. Gradualism on the other hand, the policy which Romania was trying but didn't succeed to adapt, is made up by step-by-step reforms, and moves at a slower pace, which reduces immediate economic shocks. It is a controlled transition with partial privatization and slower liberalization. Starting with 1990 prices were only partially liberalized and many controls remained. On top of that, privatization was very slow, and many industries remained state owned. This directly resulted in inflation, shortages, and a decrease

in production. It kept going until 1991 without any clear reform progress. Partial headways were made following the next 4 years, when privatization laws were starting to get introduced, but unfortunately, they were applied unevenly. Loss incurring state enterprises were kept alive using subsidies, inflation stayed high, and unemployment rose, as mentioned before. It was clear that Romania 's economy was stagnant. It is only after the EU and the IMF that Romania attempted to finally apply tougher reforms. Due to increased pressure and expectations, we adapted faster privatization subsidy cuts and trade liberalization, from 1997 to 1999. As I mentioned before, a side effect of shock therapy or a more restrictive and faster acting policy is an instant economic decline. The tougher reforms triggered another recession as previously seen in the GDP (-6.1% in 1997 with -4.8% in 1998) but this finally pushed Romania towards a functioning market economy. Perhaps if we introduced shock therapy from the beginning we would've bounced back faster, like Poland did. In January 1990 Poland introduced the "Balcerowicz plan" which freed prices overnight, ended subsidies for unprofitable state firms (something that took us years to do), liberated trade and stabilized currency. Obviously, it wasn't exactly optimal; the GDP collapsed by 7% in 1990 reaching around -11% in 1991, the inflation rate rose astronomically to 585% in 1990 and unemployment rose to 12%. However, they started recovering that very next year. By 1992 GDP returned to 2% and by 1993 growth was solid, reaching 3.8%. Poland s GDP then grew by 5-7% annually between 1994 and 1997, which made it the fastest growing post-communist economy in Europe. By the mid 1990s Poland's economy had surpassed its 1989 level, meaning it fully recovered from the transition crisis in about 3-4 years, which is incredible and the reason it is seen as the success story of shock therapy in eastern Europe. To put things into perspective, Romania only gained back its 1989 GDP level in 2004, meaning it took us approximately 15 years to recover. On the bright side, the results are definitely visible, and we are heading for sure in the direction of an even further upward trend:

- In the 1990's electricity blackouts happened multiple times each day, heating and hot water were only available for a few hours; during communism, the government controlled even the allowed temperature in our houses, scheduling regular controls to check the heaters and even restricted the amount of artificial light civilians were allowed (one light bulb of 40w for the whole apartment). Now Romania has not only stabilized its energy supply and eliminated almost entirely power blackouts but is moving towards a cleaner modern system.

- Back then, parents were worried about their children's future because factories were shutting down, now Romania not only excels in the Technology industry but also creates the opportunity for careers in any desirable sector available, not only nationally, but in other countries as well.
- Life expectancy grew by more than 10 years, child mortality fell by 2/3 and millions of Romanians escaped poverty.
- Foreign investment was scarce, as Romania was seen as unstable and risky; now it's much higher as our EU membership gave us credibility and stability
- Living standards bettered; we went from low to high wages, and from having poor to EU-funded infrastructure.
- European markets boosted exports (for e.g. cars, IT, agriculture) and the EU single market allowed us to ease the path to modernization and faster growth.

And there are a lot more. Because of the way Romania reacted to the post-communist transition, the Romanian government had a much better understanding of how the economy will react to certain policies, which helped us immensely during the 2008 global financial crisis. Yes, it shook the country, and brought back memories which I'm sure most of the people that were alive during the 40s-90s wish to forget and never relive again, but because of that, the government acted decisively, implementing one of the largest post crisis fiscal consolidation efforts in the EU. We introduced fiscal austerity, IMF-EU financial support, monetary easing and strong structural reforms which stabilized the economy. Banking regulations combined with foreign owned banks helped prevent another systemic collapse. By the end of 2012, GDP growth returned, and as of 2025, Romania is still moderately stable, even if it faces ongoing challenges like slow GDP growth (0.9% in 2024, with projected 1.4% in 2025 and 2.2% in 2026), inflation (5.8% in 2024, but expected below 4% by 2026) and unemployment (projected to decrease to around 5% by 2026).

Romania's eventual stabilization and growth after a period of crisis, eventually came from a combination of external assistance, domestic reforms, and institutional restructuring. Key macroeconomic strategies included monetary stabilization (tightening the money supply and implementing interest rate policy helped bring down hyperinflation, restore confidence in the currency, and allow real purchasing power to stabilize), fiscal consolidation (reducing budget deficits through controlled public spending and reforming subsidies that were deemed unsustainable), structural reforms (privatization of state-owned enterprises, liberalization of markets, and promotion of competition realigned incentives and improved efficiency), external

assistance and integration (IMF programs, EU pre-accession funds, and gradual alignment with European regulations facilitated macroeconomic stabilization and long-term investment, therefore accelerating integration into the global economy) and labour market adaptation (retraining programs and flexible employment policies addressed to fix structural unemployment, improving the allocation of human capital).

In the end, these measures not only facilitated but were deemed crucial in Romania's heading path towards an upwards trend by restoring long term growth potential. Romania's experience and history is a perfect example of how important the coordination between macroeconomic events and structural interventions is in ending or managing crises.

Thank you for reading my essay, I hope you enjoyed it!

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